

Anxiety & Endodontic Treatment

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Our goal is to provide the highest standard of endodontic treatment while ensuring that the experience is as comfortable as possible. Despite advances in endodontic treatment procedures, root canal treatment is still associated with anxiety and fear. Dental treatment is often stressful for patients and can evoke dental fear or dental anxiety. Preoperative fear and anxiety have been identified as distinct emotional states and are a significant problem for patients and dental care providers alike. Together, they can be a significant contributor to refusal of dental treatment and deterioration of oral and dental health.

By definition, fear and anxiety act as a signal of danger, or threat, to trigger appropriate adaptive responses. Dental fear occurs as a normal reaction to a threat or hazard that the individual perceives. Dental anxiety is a state of apprehension in which the individual senses that something unpleasant is going to happen in association with treatment. Fear is aroused by specific external stimuli, whereas anxiety is a generalized response to an unknown threat or internal conflict. Therefore, some patients may feel afraid of dental care because of past experiences, while others may have anxiety related to uncertainty of events to come. Nevertheless, dental anxiety and dental fear are highly correlated. Research indicates that dental anxiety is a mental health issue and a public health concern. The need for endodontic treatment is recognized as being particularly stressful for patients, and frequently evokes dental anxiety. The identification of patients with dental anxiety and its management are important components of care for patients receiving endodontic treatment.

Despite advances in dentistry, many people still consider root canal treatment a highly unpleasant experience. Among dental events, endodontic treatment ranked seventh among procedures that were most fear-arousing. A recent public opinion commissioned by the American Association of Endodontists on most common public fears showed that 59% of those sampled were more afraid of undergoing root canal treatment than speaking in public. The most persistent myth about root canal treatment is extreme pain. However, ~96% of patients with a history of root canal treatment would be willing to have another root canal treatment if needed.

Origins of Dental Anxiety

Dental anxiety is the result of direct and/or indirect conditioning. Direct conditioning occurs in association with a prior negative/traumatic experience, such as pain. Indirect conditioning has several pathways. These include information learned from parents (parental indirect conditioning), second-hand reports/learning (informative), being threatened with a visit to the dentist for bad behaviour (verbal threat) and assimilating negative visual images in the media (visual vicarious). In one study with almost 600 patients receiving or treatment planned for endodontic treatment, direct conditioning and parental indirect conditioning were the main causes of dental anxiety. Indirect conditioning was a greater factor for females than males. Studies addressing patient's perceptions of anxiety toward endodontic treatment placed endodontic procedures at the top of the list on provoking patient anxiety. This emotional state can cause a patient to reject endodontic treatment in favour of tooth extraction. Interestingly, previous endodontic experiences do not increase fear; however, negative hearsay does.

Physiologic response to Dental Anxiety

Endodontic treatment creates a stressful situation for anxious patients and results in a physiologic response involving the autonomic nervous system. Patients self-reported their stress levels prior to endodontic treatment, and their heart rates, systolic and diastolic blood pressures were measured before, during and after treatment. A correlation was found for pre-treatment dental anxiety and the level of physiologic stress. In addition, stress levels decreased during the appointment. In another study, patients' heart rate variability (HRV) increased prior to endodontic treatment, as a result of stress.

Outcomes of Dental Anxiety

Outcomes of dental anxiety include avoidance and postponement of dental visits. In one study, 18% of patients reported postponing endodontic treatment. Not surprisingly, patients with high levels of dental anxiety/dental fear attend irregularly or only when in pain, and tend to have poor oral health. Treating patients with DA can require extra time and be more difficult. Dental anxiety may also impact the type and treatment provided, thereby creating a barrier to the provision of quality care. Further, it can negatively impact quality of life, including social interactions.

Managing patients with Dental Anxiety

Interventions to manage dental anxiety are warranted. These should be tailored to the patient's level of dental anxiety, requiring that patients first be evaluated. For patients with relatively low levels of dental anxiety, nonpharmacological options such as pleasant scents, rapport building, giving the patient a sense of control during treatment and cognitive distraction are available. For patients with moderate levels of dental anxiety, also providing more information about endodontic treatment and what they will experience can reduce dental anxiety and fear of pain. Additional interventions can be utilized as indicated for patients with moderate/severe dental anxiety, including cognitive behavioural therapy.

Nonpharmacological interventions include relaxation therapy, systematic desensitization through exposure to stressful situations to decrease dental anxiety, computer-assisted relaxation learning to change behaviours, hypnosis, and distraction. In a systematic review of 29 trials with almost 3,000 patients, hypnosis was found to be effective in reducing stress. Distraction may consist of visual distraction, audio-visual tools such as virtual reality headsets, or music. In a recent randomized, controlled study, music decreased diastolic and systolic blood pressure and heart rate in patients undergoing endodontic treatment, signifying lowered levels of both stress and DA. In a second study, music also was found to reduce salivary levels of cortisol. In addition, psychological interventions have been shown to increase dental visit attendance, with one systematic review finding that more than three quarters of patients were regular attenders for at least four years after the intervention.

Pharmacological interventions include oral premedication with anxiolytics (e.g., benzodiazepines), conscious sedation and general anaesthesia. With respect to pharmacological interventions, their relative efficacy, mechanisms of action, side effects and contraindications must be considered, and directions for use adhered to. In addition, regulations and recommendations relevant to your location and dental license must be followed. Interprofessional collaboration and referral for medical management may be required in the treatment of patients who experience dental phobia.

Conclusions

Dental anxiety is a well-recognized problem for patients and clinicians, particularly in relation to endodontic treatment, and impacts oral health and ultimately quality of life. Nonpharmacological and pharmacological interventions are available to reduce dental anxiety in patients receiving endodontic treatment, as well as dental treatment in general. Patients should be evaluated for dental anxiety prior to treatment visits to enable appropriate intervention to reduce dental anxiety and thereby enhance oral health and the provision of care. In addition, more research is required on the relative benefits of different interventions for dental anxiety.